

Small Cell Carcinoma of the Ovary, Hypercalcemic Type: Case Report and Literature Review

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Abstract

Small cell carcinoma of the ovary, hypercalcemic type (SCCOHT), is an extremely rare and aggressive ovarian cancer subtype associated with SMARCA4 mutations. We report the case of a 36-year-old woman presenting with abdominal pain and distension, diagnosed with a solid-cystic ovarian mass and advanced disease with peritoneal and lymphatic dissemination. Exploratory laparotomy and pathological analysis confirmed SCCOHT, FIGO stage IIIC, with loss of SMARCA4 expression. The patient received initial chemotherapy with a PEB regimen, achieving partial response but subsequent disease progression. Following this, she was switched to carboplatin and etoposide without success. The disease progressed rapidly, involving mediastinal and retroperitoneal lymph nodes. In the terminal stage, palliative care measures were prioritized, and the patient passed away eight months after symptom onset. SCCOHT poses significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. The tumor's genomic stability and sensitivity to epigenetic modulators present promising opportunities for the development of targeted therapies. This case underscores the importance of early diagnosis, interdisciplinary management, and the need for innovative therapeutic strategies for this highly aggressive disease.

Introduction

Small cell carcinoma of the ovary, hypercalcemic type (SCCOHT), is an extremely rare and aggressive subtype of ovarian cancer, predominantly affecting young women. It accounts for less than 0.01% of malignant ovarian tumors, with fewer than 500 cases documented to date. SCCOHT is characteristically associated with elevated serum calcium levels and somatic mutations in the SMARCA4 gene [1].

This subtype is frequently marked by paraneoplastic hypercalcemia and SMARCA4 mutations, identified in over 95% of cases diagnosed since its discovery in 2014 [2].

SCCOHT was first recognized as a distinct entity in 1979 by R. Scully and was classified as a miscellaneous tumor in the 2014 WHO guidelines. Clinically, it presents as a rapidly growing pelvic mass with nonspecific symptoms such as abdominal pain and distension, contributing to its late diagnosis and poor prognosis [3,4]. Five-year survival rates range from 33% in stage IA to less than 10% in more advanced stages, with a median age at diagnosis of 24 years [1].

Although multimodal therapeutic approaches, including cytoreductive surgery, platinum-based chemotherapy, and radiotherapy, have been proposed, the lack of standardized international guidelines limits progress in the management of SCCOHT. Recently, molecular analysis and targeted therapies have opened new avenues for research and treatment of this pathology [1,4].

Case Report

A 36-year-old woman, with no relevant personal or family medical history, presented with diffuse abdominal pain lasting several days, accompanied by abdominal distension, nausea, and vomiting. On physical examination, a mobile, tender mass measuring approximately 6 cm was palpated in the lower abdomen.

Transvaginal ultrasound revealed a 121x100 mm solid-cystic adnexal mass in the left ovary, with irregular borders and free fluid in the cul-de-sac. MRI confirmed a pathological cystic lesion in the left ovary, with nodular peritoneal thickening, solid nodules in the omentum, pelvis, and subphrenic areas, as well as

More Information

How to cite this article: Camejo N, Rivero L, Castillo C, Krygier G. Small Cell Carcinoma of the Ovary, Hypercalcemic Type: Case Report and Literature Review. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2025;3(1):45-8.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(1).08

Keywords:

Small Cell Carcinoma,
Ovarian Neoplasms,
Hypercalcemia,
SMARCA4 Protein,
Chemotherapy,
SCCOHT.

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lateroaortic and iliac lymphadenopathy (up to 4 cm) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. MRI of the Abdomen and Pelvis Showing a Complex Mass in the Left Ovary. Signs of Diffuse Secondary Peritoneal Involvement and Abdominal Wall Involvement are Evident

During exploratory laparotomy, a ruptured right ovarian tumor with spillage of its contents into the peritoneal cavity was identified. A right adnexectomy was performed (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Right Ovarian Tumor Showing Signs of Distress

The pathological anatomy report describes a fragmented right ovary (450 g) with friable solid grayish areas, extensive hemorrhagic zones, and necrosis. Microscopically, it shows diffuse proliferation of small cells arranged in nests, cords, and sheets, with basophilic cytoplasm in most cells and eosinophilic cytoplasm in some areas. The stroma presents desmoplastic reaction and lymphocytic infiltration. The neoplasm involves all submitted material, making it challenging to assess capsular invasion. Immunohistochemistry: KI-67 at 80%, SMARCA4 loss, BRG1 negative, WT1 and PAX8 positive, Inhibin negative, CK 5/6 negative, CD99 positive, EMA positive, focal calretinin positive, CD10 positive. Negative results for ACL, MELAN A, CKI8718, Chromogranin, Synaptophysin, CK7, and hormonal receptors.

The histomorphology and immunohistochemical profile are consistent with a primary small cell carcinoma of the ovary, suggesting the hypercalcemic subtype, characterized by extensive areas of hemorrhage and necrosis and the presence of a SMARCA4 (BRG1) mutation.

Subsequent chest, abdomen, and pelvis CT scans revealed lymphatic dissemination and peritoneal carcinomatosis, classifying the disease as FIGO stage IIIC. The tumor board recommended initiating neoadjuvant chemotherapy with the PEB regimen.

After three cycles of PEB with regular tolerance, the patient achieved a major partial response but developed extensive deep vein thrombosis, delaying surgery for one month. Tumor progression was later identified.

Due to disease progression, chemotherapy was switched to carboplatin (AUC 5) and etoposide. After one cycle, the patient was admitted with respiratory symptoms, revealing new lymphatic progression involving mediastinal and retroperitoneal adenopathies, peritoneal nodules, and partial compression of the superior vena cava. A family meeting was held to explain the terminal stage of the disease, prioritizing comfort measures. The patient developed refractory pain and respiratory failure, initiating palliative sedation. She passed away days later, eight months after the onset of symptoms.

Discussion

The complexity of managing SCCOHT lies not only in its rarity but also in its aggressiveness and the lack of standardized international guidelines. While the therapeutic approach includes cytoreductive surgery, platinum-based chemotherapy, and, in some cases, radiotherapy or high-dose chemotherapy with autologous stem cell transplantation, survival outcomes remain unsatisfactory in advanced stages [4]. In this context, comprehensive evaluation of patients by multidisciplinary tumor boards, as demonstrated in this case, enables therapeutic decisions to be tailored according to the specific characteristics of the disease and the initial treatment response [3].

Although SMARCA4 mutations are present in over 95% of SCCOHT cases and represent a key pathogenic factor, their occurrence is generally sporadic. However, familial aggregation has been reported in some cases, suggesting a possible hereditary genetic predisposition. In our patient, the absence of a family history of cancer aligns with the variability in familial expression of this mutation. This finding underscores the importance of conducting genetic analyses in patients diagnosed with SCCOHT, even in those without a family history of cancer, as SMARCA4 mutations can arise de novo and significantly contribute to the tumor's aggressiveness [1].

SMARCA4 mutation plays a crucial role in the carcinogenesis of SCCOHT. In our patient, immunohistochemistry revealed a loss of SMARCA4 expression, suggesting inactivation of BRG1, a key component of the SWI/SNF complex. This alteration disrupts chromatin structure, promoting uncontrolled tumor proliferation. In addition to explaining the tumor's aggressiveness and rapid progression, this mutation represents a potential therapeutic target, highlighting the promise of epigenetic modulators as future options for managing these cases [5].

In addition to SMARCA4, genomic alterations such as overexpression of MAGEA4, AURKB, and CLDN6 have been identified as potential therapeutic targets. These open the door to strategies such as immunotherapy and epigenetic therapies, particularly relevant in addressing chemotherapy resistance in SCCOHT relapses. Incorporating these targets could improve the prognosis of this rare and aggressive disease [6].

SCCOHT exhibits distinctive pathological features that aid in its differential diagnosis. Macroscopically, these tumors are described as large (average of 15 cm), yellowish in color, with solid areas, necrosis, hemorrhage, and cystic degeneration, as observed in this case and reported in the literature [1,7].

Microscopically, SCCOHT exhibits variability in cell size, with moderate to abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm, a feature also present in our patient. Additionally, these tumors may occasionally contain foci of benign-appearing mucinous epithelium, which adds complexity to their histopathological evaluation [1,7].

SCCOHT is predominantly diagnosed in young women, as in this case, with a mean age of 24 years and a peak incidence in the second and third decades of life [1].

Hypercalcemia, present in 62% of SCCOHT cases, is associated with a paraneoplastic mechanism involving the production of PTH-related proteins. Although generally asymptomatic, its incidental detection can contribute to the differential diagnosis and provide insights into tumor aggressiveness. In our patient, serum calcium was not evaluated at the time of diagnosis, likely due to the rarity of this entity in our setting [8].

The differential diagnosis of SCCOHT includes neoplasms such as lymphoma, granulosa cell tumor, and dysgerminoma, due to morphological similarities and growth patterns in young patients [5,8]. In this case, a germ cell or epithelial tumor was initially suspected, but the loss of SMARCA4 expression on immunohistochemistry was key to confirming the diagnosis of SCCOHT, differentiating it from other ovarian neoplasms.

Early dissemination is a common feature of SCCOHT, with frequent metastases to the pelvis and abdomen, as observed in this case [7].

Tumor stage at diagnosis is the primary determinant of prognosis in SCCOHT, with advanced disease carrying a very poor outlook. Only one-third of patients with stage IA remain disease-free, while most with advanced stages succumb within the first two years, regardless of treatment. Factors such as age >30 years, normal calcium levels, tumor size <10 cm, and absence of large cells are associated with better prognosis in stage IA [1,3,8]. In this case, despite favorable age and normal calcium levels, the outcome was poor due to the advanced stage at diagnosis, reaffirming its critical impact on prognosis.

The rarity of SCCOHT and the lack of prospective trials make it challenging to establish a standard treatment protocol. However, a multimodal approach involving optimal cytoreductive surgery, chemotherapy, and, in selected cases, radiotherapy (RT) is recommended. Although RT indications are not clearly defined, recent studies suggest its potential benefit in recurrences and as an adjuvant following chemotherapy and surgery, improving local control and survival in advanced stages or with residual tumor. Its inclusion should be carefully evaluated based on the risk-benefit balance [1,9,10].

SCCOHT exhibits transient chemosensitivity, rapid progression, and limited response in recurrences, making platinum-based chemotherapy the recommended option. Although there is no standard protocol, regimens such as BEP (bleomycin, etoposide, cisplatin) and VPCBAE (vinblastine, cisplatin, cyclophosphamide, bleomycin, doxorubicin, and etoposide) have shown better outcomes. High-dose chemotherapy (HDC) with autologous stem cell transplantation is also an option following an initial complete response. Despite higher toxicity, it is associated with improved overall survival ($p < 0.001$) [9-11].

In this case, the patient was discussed in an interdisciplinary tumor board, and due to her advanced disease with peritoneal dissemination, the PEB regimen was chosen, followed by cytoreductive surgery if a response to systemic treatment was achieved. A consolidation strategy with hematopoietic stem cell transplantation could have been considered, given the high recurrence rate, although its efficacy in SCCOHT remains under study, showing benefits in patients with advanced disease [1].

The patient initiated chemotherapy with the PEB regimen but exhibited poor response and only regular tolerance due to hematological side effects. Upon disease progression, her case was re-evaluated in the tumor board, and treatment with carboplatin (AUC 5) and etoposide was initiated, based on second-line options described in the literature. However, the patient showed poor tolerance and rapid progression, consistent with the short-duration responses reported

in SCCOHT, even with multi-agent chemotherapy [1,3,9-11].

SCCOHT tumors are an excellent example of malignant tumors where the development of new targeted therapies is possible. In this context, several clinical trials have been conducted based on immunotherapy, CDK 4/6 inhibitors, and epigenetic therapies, which have shown promising results [10]. Despite their characteristically aggressive course, these tumors have demonstrated genomic stability and low mutational burden, with a remarkably homogeneous genomic profile [12]. In vitro data support the view that SCCOHTs are sensitive to epigenetic modulators, justifying further exploration of epigenetic treatment strategies for this lethal disease [13].

Conclusion

SCCOHT is a rare and highly aggressive ovarian cancer, particularly in young patients with tumors associated with hypercalcemia. Testing for SMARCA4 mutations is essential for diagnosis and the development of new therapeutic options.

The prognosis remains poor, with radical surgery being the only curative possibility in localized cases. Current therapies, such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy, provide limited efficacy, and there is no standard treatment. Although most SCCOHTs exhibit loss of SMARCA4 expression, no specific targeted therapies are yet available. Research into epigenetic strategies could open new avenues for more effective treatment of this aggressive disease.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

The author(s) received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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